

A serious skin viral disease in cattle- Lumpy Skin Disease (LSD)

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Introduction

In the Indian subcontinent countries, including India, Pakistan, Bangladesh, Nepal, Sri Lanka and Bhutan, are currently facing a deadly viral epidemic in the cattle population. The disease is called lumpy skin disease (LSD), which is caused by a *Capripoxvirus* (family *Poxviridae*) called lumpy skin disease virus (LSDV). LSD is primarily a disease of cattle; buffaloes develop only mild illness [1]. Other domestic animals are considered to be resistant to LSDV infection [2]. The disease is characterized by fever, enlargement of the lymph nodes, anorexia, depression, dysgalactia, emaciation and development of skin nodules (10–50 mm in size) that can lead to a sharp decline in milk production, abortion in pregnant animal and sterility in bulls [3].

History & Outbreaks

For many decades since its first report from Zambia (Africa) in 1929 [4], LSD was confined to the African countries. Since 2012, LSD has spread from Africa into several countries in Europe. In Asia, it was first reported in 2019 in North West China, Bangladesh, and India [3,5,6] and then in 2020, it spreads across many countries, including Bhutan, Myanmar, Nepal, Hong Kong, Vietnam, Taiwan and Sri Lanka. For a period of about 2-3 years since its introduction into India, incidences of LSD were mainly observed in the Eastern part of the country without any significant mortality. The current wave of the LSD, which was started from the Western Indian states of Gujarat and Rajasthan in June/July 2022, is highly lethal. According to the Department of Animal Husbandry and Dairying, Government of India, as of 30 September 2022, LSD has spread across 251 districts in 15 states and has affected over 2 million animals including 11 lakh deaths [7]. The milk production was decreased by more than 26% in the affected states [7]. If LSD continues, India and other countries in the region will face a major milk shortage. Livestock farming is the mainstay of the small and marginal farmers (>85% of the total farmers) in the subcontinent. The maximum number of deaths due to LSD has occurred in

lactating and pregnant cattle, which serve as a direct source of income in terms of the sale of milk and produce progeny, thereby adversely affecting the livelihood of poor farmers in the region. The direct livestock and production losses due to LSD in the Asian countries are estimated to be worth up to \$1.46 billion [8].

In contrast to the recent LSD outbreaks, which are associated with high mortality, LSD is usually not associated with high mortality rate [9]. Although the exact molecular mechanism of high pathogenicity of LSDV/2022 strain currently circulating in India and other South Asian countries needs to be determined and preliminary observations (post-mortem findings) suggest that high mortality may be due to the capacity of the virus (LSDV/2022) to cause severe hemorrhages and extensive nodule formation in the visceral organs, especially in lungs.

Causative agent

LSDV belongs to the genus *Capripoxvirus* of the family *Poxviridae*. Two other Capri pox viruses, sheep pox virus (SPV) and goat pox virus (GPV), which cause similar diseases in sheep and goats, respectively, are genetically and antigenically quite similar and cannot be distinguished from each other serologically. Heterologous vaccines (based on SPV or GPV) are usually authorized for use to induce cross protection against LSDV in cattle, particularly in instances where a homologous (LSDV-based) vaccine is not available. The Government of India also authorized the use of a heterologous vaccine (GPV-based) against LSD in cattle. However, heterologous vaccines are less efficacious and only provide partial protection [10].

Vaccines against LSDV

The National Centre for Veterinary Type Cultures in Hisar (India), in collaboration with the Indian Veterinary Research Institute in Izatnagar (India) developed a homologous live-attenuated LSD vaccine, named Lumpi-ProVac^{Ind} (currently commercially available). The virus used for developing the vaccine was isolated from skin scab collected from naturally LSDV-infected cattle from Ranchi (India) in 2019 (Kenyan-type LSDV strain). The virus was attenuated by continuous cell culture passaging (50 times in Vero cells). The experimental vaccination trials in calves suggested that the vaccine was safe, could induce potent levels of antibody- and cell-mediated immune response and provided a complete level of protection against virulent LSDV infection in cattle. As part of phase III clinical trials, the vaccine has been administered in over 25,000 animals in different geographical regions in India. The vaccine has been found to be safe in cattle and buffaloes of all age groups including lactating/pregnant animals and bulls.

Lumpi-ProVac^{Ind} can be considered for use to replace the existing goat pox vaccination practice against LSD in cattle in India. Since the Kenyan-type LSDV strain is predominantly circulating in South Asia, the Lumpi-ProVac^{Ind} could prove to be a better option for the control and eradication of LSD in the region.

References

- [1]. Elhaig MM, Selim A, Mahmoud M. Lumpy skin disease in cattle: frequency of occurrence in a dairy farm and a preliminary assessment of its possible impact on Egyptian buffaloes. *Onderstepoort J Vet Res.* 2017;84 (1):e1–6.
- [2]. Sprygin A, Pestova Y, Wallace DB, et al. Transmission of lumpy skin disease virus: a short review. *Virus Res.* 2019;269:197637.
- [3]. Kumar N, Chander Y, Kumar R, et al. Isolation and characterization of lumpy skin disease virus from cattle in India. *PLoS One.* 2021;16(1):e0241022.
- [4]. Ras M. Pseudo-Urticaria of Cattle. Government of Northern Rhodesia: Department of Animal Health; 1931. p. 20–21.
- [5]. Tran HTT, Truong AD, Dang AK, et al. Lumpy skin disease outbreaks in Vietnam, 2020. *Transbound Emerg Dis.* 2021;68(3):977–980.
- [6]. Roche X, Rozstalnyy A, TagoPacheco D, et al. Introduction and spread of lumpy skin disease in South, East and Southeast Asia: qualitative risk assessment and management. Rome: FAO animal production and health; 2020.
- [7]. Shagun. Lump skin disease has created a livelihood crisis for India’s small dairy farmers. *DownToEarth*; 2022 Sep 30. Available from: <https://www.downtoearth.org.in/news/economy/ground-report-lumpy-skin-disease-has-created-a-livelihood-crisis-for-india-s-small-dairy-farmers-85245>.
- [8]. Azeem S, Sharma B, Shabir S, et al. Lumpy skin disease is expanding its geographic range: a challenge for Asian livestock management and food security. *Vet J.* 2022;279:105785.
- [9]. Casal J, Allepuz A, Miteva A, et al. Economic cost of lumpy skin disease outbreaks in three Balkan countries: Albania, Bulgaria and the Former Yugoslav Republic of Macedonia (2016-2017). *Transbound Emerg Dis.* 2018;65(6):1680–1688.
- [10]. Abutarbush SM, Tuppurainen ESM. Serological and clinical evaluation of the Yugoslavian RM65 sheep pox strain vaccine use in cattle against lumpy skin disease. *Transbound Emerg Dis.* 2018;65(6):1657–1663.

